

Conceptualizing of Priorities in the Dynamics of Public Administration Contemporary Reforms

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Abstract—The article presents the results of the creative analysis and comparison of trends in the development of the theory of public administration during the period from the second half of the 20th to the beginning of the 21st century. The process of conceptualization of the priorities of public administration in the dynamics of reforming was held under the influence of such factors as globalization, integration, information and technological changes and human rights is examined. The priorities of the social state in the concepts of the second half of the 20th century are studied. Peculiar approaches to determining the priorities of public administration in the countries of "Soviet dictatorship" in Central and Eastern Europe in the same period are outlined. Particular attention is paid to the priorities of public administration regarding the interaction between public power and society and the development of conceptual foundations for the modern managerial process. There is a thought that the dynamics of the formation of concepts of the European governance is characterized by the sequence of priorities: from socio-economic and moral-ethical to organizational-procedural and non-hierarchical ones. The priorities of the "welfare state" were focused on the decent level of material wellbeing of population. At the same time, the conception of "minimal state" emphasized priorities of human responsibility for their own fate under the conditions of minimal state protection. Later on, the emphasis was placed on horizontal ties and redistribution of powers and competences of "effective state" with its developed procedures and limits of responsibility at all levels of government and in close cooperation with the civil society. The priorities of the contemporary period are concentrated on human rights in the concepts of "good governance" and all the following ones, which recognize the absolute priority of public administration with compliance, provision and protection of human rights. There is a proved point of view that civilizational changes taking place under the influence of information and technological imperatives also stipulate changes in priorities, redistribution of emphases and update principles of managerial concepts on the basis of publicity, transparency, departure from traditional forms of hierarchy and control in favor of interactivity and inter-sectoral interaction, decentralization and humanization of managerial processes. The necessity to permanently carry out the reorganization, by establishing the interaction between different participants of public power and social relations, to establish a balance between political forces and social interests on the basis of mutual trust and mutual understanding determines changes of social, political, economic and humanitarian paradigms of public administration and their theoretical comprehension. The further studies of theoretical foundations of modern public administration in interdisciplinary discourse in the context of ambiguous consequences of the globalizational and integrational processes of modern European state-building would be advisable. This is especially true during the period of political transformations and economic crises which are the characteristic of the contemporary Europe, especially for democratic transition countries.

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I. INTRODUCTION

SCIENTIFIC concepts and strategies for the development of European countries in the post-war period were developed in the scientific works of well-known European researchers based on the scientific methodology of various scientific fields, in particular, economics, political science, jurisprudence, sociology and methodology of public administration. The introduction of these concepts or the approaches based on them to state-building processes, formation of state policy, definition of economic priorities, their levers and methods of their implementation at the national level have allowed European countries to achieve significant progress in public construction and in the development of economy and infrastructure. An analysis of these scientific concepts makes it possible to make certain generalizations about the purpose-setting of governments, options for implementing concepts and their real results.

The important aspects of the theory of public administration have been developed by researchers such as Boston [14], Buchanan [15], Dullien and Guérot [1], Erhard [2], Esping-Andersen [4], Havel [8], Klingebiel [20], Kooiman [18], Pierson [5] and others.

Developed European countries have always been seeking the most productive models of public administration in order to renew traditional ones, which were formed in accordance with historical, political, administrative, cultural, and religious characteristics and stereotypes of previous eras. Both pessimistic and optimistic assessments of modern public management are usually based on the interdisciplinary approaches of economists, political scientists, sociologists, philosophers and accumulate in the science of public administration, providing sufficient argumentation and expanding the research methodology.

Theoretical substantiation of public administration takes into account the peculiarities of the formation of the state system and the way of functioning of the state administration of the countries in which these features have become characteristic. The vast majority of sources on the theory of state administration in the second half of the 20th century offered to associate management models with the traditional division of scholarly schools into American, British, German, and French. Optional to these concepts were added North-European - Scandinavian, and Pyrenean, or South-European models. The most general characteristic of each of them was

mainly the determination of the essential features and characteristic approaches in the relationship and interaction of man with the state, the state with society, the public with the state and the individual.

Despite the considerable interest of scientists in the theoretical problems of public administration, there is still no consensus in the scientific literature on the ability of certain, territorially or disciplined-oriented theoretical approaches to the problems of ensuring the effectiveness of public administration in practice.

There are a number of universal factors, among which, in particular, globalization, integration processes in Europe, information revolution, the latest achievements in the field of management and management technologies, which explains the desire for mutual enrichment and universalization of the scientific concepts of modern state governance. At the same time, the main traditions of the European management culture, socioeconomic and political conditions which are roughly identical to the most developed European countries, if we bear in mind the processes of decentralization and democratization of the authorities, remain significant regional factors. Specific socio-cultural factors - traditions, customs, psycho-emotional peculiarities of the population, individual for every European country - significantly affect the situation, becoming even demonstrative, under the influence of globalization and the imperatives of the expediency, efficiency and effectiveness of public administration both at national and integration levels. One way or another, the main priority of reforming the power systems in relation to approaches and mechanisms of public administration is to increase the efficiency of power in the context of meeting the needs of the community in professional qualified government.

II. PRIORITIES OF THE SOCIAL STATE IN THE CONCEPTIONS OF THE 2ND HALF OF THE 20TH CENTURY

In the conceptions of the state administration of the second half of the 20th century, for a long time the priority was a social component, which quite naturally played a decisive role in post-war Europe. It was important to mobilize the efforts of all - government, entrepreneurship, and civil society - to restore normal conditions for the functioning of social institutions and further development on the basis of social interaction. A striking example of the result of such efforts can be the model of a social market state, created as a result of the implementation of the concept of Erhard in West Germany in the early 1950's, based on the ideas of the Ordoliberalism of W. Eucken Freiburg school [1]. In general, the Ordoliberals advocated a free market mechanism through state intervention, and not as opposed to it. They saw the basis of economic prosperity in strengthening economic order - the coordinated activity of all social institutions that dictate the rules of a free market. Key functions in this context relied on the state, whose intervention was not to substitute the functioning of market mechanisms, but to create conditions for their functioning, to ensure that free enterprise and competition would naturally select the most effective forms of reproduction and restore the balance of supply and demand. A

feasible economic order based on free competition that ensures the efficiency of the market system and free prices as a regulatory tool in a competitive environment and a unique lever of redistribution of resources between sectors of production ensured the stability of money, free access to markets, and guarantee of private property, stability and consistency of the economic policy.

Thus, the market, not wild or barbaric, but free and organized, socially responsible, opposed to political and economic suppression of an individuals and violation of their rights, made it possible to develop a model of "social market economy" in theory and in practice. The essence of this model was well-formulated by Ehrhard: "the historic task of the Federal Republic in the second half of the 20th century that we have just entered upon is to underpin, to strengthen and to defend the free economic order of Europe with the full weight of German trade. The successful rehabilitation of my country must serve as clear documentary evidence to put before the still vacillating and doubting peoples, of the fact that only by firmly rejecting socialist dogmas, of whatever complexion, and by affirming 'a free economic order can mounting prosperity and genuine security be achieved. In a Europe which allowed the life of the individual to be dragooned into ever more regimented collectives, the intellectual and spiritual powers would atrophy powers that are vitally necessary in order to combat the 'infiltration', and also the many enticements, of the East" [2].

The implementation of the concept brought more than impressive results, the most significant of which were, in particular, unprecedented economic growth, which was 9-10% per year in the early 1950s, and in 1953-1956, up to 10-15% per year; second place among the Western industrial production countries (only in the late 1960s Western Germany was pushed by Japan); the German currency became the strongest in Europe; in the second half of the 1950s unemployment virtually disappeared, while real incomes rose threefold. The economic system chosen by Erhard, where liberal market mechanisms are consistent with the purposeful state tax and credit policy, has proven effective. Of course, for the implementation of investment programs, the government had a powerful financial fund, the basis of which was laid by the measures of the Marshall Plan. The absence of military expenditures also played its role. Thus, the promising policy of the state in the social sphere and in the field of labor relations allowed providing sustainable consumer demand, which was of fundamental importance for the effective functioning of a liberalized economy.

In March 1965, Ehrhard proposed the concept of a "formed society", which, in the conditions crisis of "consumption society", prognosticated by the author, was meant to initiate the search for ways to humanize all spheres of public life, emphasizing that the criteria of social welfare are not reduced exclusively to indicators of production, consumption and economic growth. In fact, the concept of "formed society" was one of the forms of ideological justification of the "welfare state" model, which, in the context of the "1960s crisis", proved to be ineffective both in economic and ideological

terms.

The American version of the Welfare State concept was proposed by Galbraith [3]. It has become the official doctrine of the United States since the early 1950s. The heyday of the implementation of the doctrine fell to the second half of the 1960s and the first half of the 1970s, when the growth of social spending in the country peaked in the history of the United States. The Keynesian tradition associated with the elaboration of the principles of macroeconomic analysis and the justification of the theory of state regulation of a market economy was the basis for its realization.

The generalization and typification of the "welfare state" experience is largely associated with the name of Esping-Andersen [4], who has highlighted the foundations common for most social doctrines of European concepts of state governance, in particular, the nature of state intervention, the stratification of social groups and the threshold, after which the market division was replaced by a bureaucratic distribution of benefits. On the basis of these parameters, scientists have identified three types of the welfare state: neoliberal (American), socio-democratic (Scandinavian), conservative-corporatist (French-German). Esping-Andersen's conclusions have become the basis for many theorists in an interdisciplinary context; remaining the same now to a certain extent.

Western countries in the second half of the 20th century implemented different versions of the concept of public administration with a basic social component; that is, with a predominant emphasis on the social sphere. However, the financial problems faced by most economically developed countries in the beginning and in the mid-1980s left certain traces on the tendencies in the implementation of the state's social functions, which resulted in the erosion of the differences between the indicated models. Thus, the states with significant amounts of financing social expenditures at the expense of the budget system began to use the social insurance system more actively and introduce elements of payment in the system of public social services. At the same time, in countries with a focus on financing social services at the expense of insurance, the tendency was to increase the participation of budget sources of financing.

An active and large-scale social policy conducted in countries with a market economy type has had a significant impact on the overall market situation, conjuncture and the rates of economic growth. In the 1980s, the issue of "retrenchment" of social spending became relevant both in conducting comparative studies and in the practice of the governments of those states that set the goal to reach "general welfare".

The intensification of discussions in the early 1990s led to the search for exit strategies from the crisis of the "welfare state". Pierson examined the policy of the UK and US governments in this direction and developed his own theory of "a new welfare state policy", according to which, the theory of socio-economic functionalism and the class theory of power do not take into account the new factors that emerged in the 21st century. Pierson singled out the characteristic features of

the welfare state and the new realities of the early 21st century, in particular, sustained public support and institutional inertia of the state [5]. The curtailment of the social obligations of the state, unpopular in society, gives politicians reason to refrain from radical reductions, and instead carry out a "policy of avoiding accusations". The crisis transformations of the last third of the 20th century have not gone unnoticed for this concept and have led to an increase in the interest in these activities on the part of civil society institutions, in particular philanthropy, which are intended to assume the responsibility for the implementation of some part of the state's social obligations.

In the 1990s, the theory of the welfare state was transformed into a methodological interpretation of the European legal culture, which revealed itself through the concept of a social state that solved the fundamental spiritual and sociocultural problem of the formation of a universally developed personality. Interpretation of the essence of the social state in these concepts demonstrated the ambiguity of the positions of Western European and American researchers. Thus, German researchers were inclined to see the prospect of realizing the social function of the state together with representatives of entrepreneurship, motivated to provide resources for social programs. The modern social state was defined as a centralized guided care to guarantee all citizens all survival needs, and based social justice on economic liberalism. The peculiarity of the modern conception of the social policy of developed countries is that its priority is to prevent the stark material and social inequality, and to provide a sufficiently high level of social support and assistance to the populations in need, by providing citizens with access to high-quality health care and education. To this end, the state actively uses budgetary funds for social programs, implements measures to develop institutions of compulsory, voluntary social and personal insurance, and becomes the central subject of social functions in the society [6].

The concept of a "minimal state" was formed on the diametrically opposite principles as for the social component of state policy and the role of the state in relation to social obligations to the population; the most notable representative of which was considered by Nozick (1938 - 2002), who opposed the concept of a social state, since the latter violated a "hypothetical social contract, in which the state should only guarantee foreign security and protection of social institutions" and cannot assume responsibility for the consequences of a social contract and change on a unilateral basis, thereby denying the sovereign the will of the other party in the concluded civil convention. According to Nozick, "people have the right to own property in relation to themselves and their labor and have the right to independently decide what will happen to them and what they will do, and also have the right to reap the fruits of their actions," reaching social equality or even just equality of opportunities is impossible without significant restriction of freedom of people. R. Nozick offered only formal and legal freedom and a formal free and fair society. To agree on some restrictions to ensure that you have more real freedom and control in your

life is a choice that every individual must make. "Sociological nominalism", supported by Nozick, interpreted the society as a simple sum of individuals and denied the existence of society as a subject, since "there are only individuals, different people, each of which has their own life" [7].

At the time of the reign of M. Thatcher (1979-1990) and her successor, J. Major, the domestic policy of Britain was to a certain extent based on the concept of a minimal state in its British version. The political philosophy and economic policy of the then-market-based model were based on deregulation, in particular of the financial system, the provision of a flexible labor market, the privatization of state-owned companies, reduction of the trade unions' influence; the freedom and self-realization of the preached by M. Thatcher, "broker-state", remained a hypothetical imperative of favorable external circumstances. The methods and results of its implementation on the basis of the policy of cost reduction, privatization and deregulation, are not devoid of significant polemical potential. In general, the concept of a minimal state meant the least possible state interference in the economy and private life on the basis of respect for rights and freedoms, mainly through "no violation".

Solving the problem of an appropriate proportion of state intervention in all spheres of society is important for every active person, since they face the need to fill out tax returns, keep tax records, pay taxes, and take part in elections, etc. The presence of the state is felt in all spheres of life, since all spheres are regulated by laws and established by state authorities. The concept of a minimal state is based on the assumption that in many spheres, the state can be replaced by a private sector capable of providing the bulk of public services. Technically, such a change is really possible provided that appropriate deregulation, denationalization and privatization are introduced.

Despite the fact that state intervention could be different both in form and in essence, and not always have negative consequences, the interrelation of interests - personal, public and state in the activity of the state - remains the subject of discussions among scholars and government officials. For many of them, the well-argued idea confirmed by daily experience of communication is that poverty as such, the lack of a desire for wealth, a career, or even just economic prosperity, if it involves the need to strain and change anything in their own lives - can be a conscious choice, dictated by a life position or just laziness. You cannot force a person to strive for what he does not want. So, to make everyone happy is not only impossible, but also not needed.

III. PECULIAR APPROACHES TO THE DEFINITION OF SOCIAL PRIORITIES IN THE COUNTRIES OF "SOVIET DICTAT" IN CENTRAL AND EASTERN EUROPE

The character of the state-building impulses of the theorists of the second half of the 20th century, who were in the conditions of the Soviet dictatorship in the countries of Central and Eastern Europe, was significantly different. Theoretical studies were mainly devoted to finding a decent exit from the "hopelessness" of "real socialism" in the plane of legal, non-

political activity, because the political one was doomed to cruel suppression. The most original ones were the concepts of well-known Czech human rights activists Havel and Benda. In particular, Havel, author of the concept of "non-political politics," considered the neglect of an individual's rights as the reason for a moral crisis which led to the crisis of society. In the conditions of socialist reality, it was necessary to adapt, because the authorities were not interested in the real ideals of people, it was only about compliance with the demands, which, in conditions of ideological pressure, resulted in the indifference of the population, disbelief in the future, questioned the possibility of changes in society. The totalitarian regime sought to ensure that people ceased to believe in the viability of fighting for the truth and their own rights, and, supporting this trend, forced citizens to refuse to participate in political life, to remain silent and to work [8].

At the heart of the societal crisis, there was a fundamental difference between what was happening in real life and the interpretation of events by the authorities. Party and state functionaries asserted that socialist democracy was the most perfect, but in everyday life, people saw that they did not have the slightest influence on solving any serious political problems, including human rights issues. Real socialism, in spite of the cheerful characteristics of the official propaganda of the regime, gave rise to a discrepancy between the essence and the facade, which, according to V. Havel, was the cause of the conflict with the authorities. Shimechka in this regard characterized the socialist reality as not corresponding to the common sense of the average population, although citizens in their everyday lives paid more attention to finding opportunities to exist in a repressive system that does not leave out any aspect of their life, using both economic and political levers for total power over each member of society. The objective conditions of everyday life of ordinary people were decisive in conditions where the economic factors made a person devoid of private property and opportunities for private initiative completely depended on the authorities [9].

The totalitarian system was self-asserting without requiring citizens to believe in its ideology and even agreeing with it: it was enough to publicly demonstrate such an agreement; that is, voluntary participation in public events such as the May Day, the anniversary of the revolution, etc. By fulfilling these demands of the authorities, every citizen encouraged others to behave in the same way; therefore, the person acted not only as the object of power, but also as the subject of the process of its realization, which was the base of the totalitarian regimes stability.

According to Havel, the communist regime forced a person to "live in untruth", and therefore, only "life in truth" could become a way out of this crisis, which every citizen could do by refusing to perform rituals, trying to overcome the discrepancy between reality and its interpretation by the power and returning to life that corresponds to its inner essence. Each citizen had to solve these problems for himself, so the border lay in the minds of each individual, and not between "us" and "them"; that is, the population and totalitarian power in the countries of the Soviet diktat, which at that time were the

countries of Central and Eastern Europe. True, authenticity and identity are categories that characterize a particular person, not the general public; therefore, only changes in each particular person could lead to changes in society, to the realization of "life in truth." Such self-awareness of one's own authenticity was considered by V. Havel as a non-political act. The social crisis was treated as an existential problem, so he distanced himself from politics as a key path to social change and society governance.

Traditional parliamentary democracy, in his opinion, could not be perceived as a political ideal, as the form tried out by the time, because it was no longer able to provide a man with a decent existence and the realization of his rights. The new post-democratic society should not rely on old, compromised structures; that is, traditional mass political parties whereas, the structure of authentic social self-organization in the new conditions will emerge from the bottom. In this way, informal open cells should be formed as a symbolic micro-model of the new post-democratic structures represented at the time by the human rights environment, a kind of "parallel society".

The principle of self-government can guarantee the direct participation of workers in solving economic problems and provide a sense of ownership for the results of social activities. Regarding the post-democratic society, V. Havel was inclined towards a certain utopian "third way", which should lead to overcoming the imperfections of bourgeois democracy and the socialist system and result in the birth of a new post-democratic social system, the nucleus of which he observed in non-political independent groups that were set up to resolve specific social problems. In the center of the state-of-the-art conception, V. Havel always had a human being endowed with an unquestionable universal right to life in the truth and a human's life, the value of which, in his opinion, is comparable to the value of life in the global sense. To a certain extent, it was the rejection of alternative political concepts, models and programs, even if they were based on democratic ideals. Solving the existential problem under the conditions of a totalitarian regime is only possible if distancing from politics as a key path of social change and society governance. Human rights are the only sufficient motivation for political theory and state-building practice. V. Havel's state-building conception was generally out of the tendencies of the Western scientific thought of that period and was ahead of its time in the other countries of Central and Eastern Europe.

The original proposal for a solution to the moral and political crisis of "real socialism" was the concept of a "parallel policy" by V. Benda [10]. He believed that the creation of a "parallel policy", a new "parallel society", could provide a dynamic and concrete perspective for the self-preservation of the national spirit, traditions, statehood and identity of the people through relative political activity embodied in the conditionality of a "parallel world". The bottom line was the creation of independent structures, which, albeit to a limited extent, could perform those functions that the existing state bodies of a totalitarian regime did not hurry to carry out their. V. Benda proposed to use structures that already existed, but initially "give them humanity." The buds

of the "parallel policy" the author saw in the existence of the so-called "parallel culture" of "samizdat" and underground, which were developed even after the oppression of the regime, and "parallel" science, to a lesser extent - the education that existed at the expense of intellectuals and creative intellectuals who were deprived of the opportunity to work professionally in a legal way, so they turned to the underground and "samizdat".

According to V. Benda, an information structure based on what was already in the underground was to become an important aspect of this activity, in which, then several thousand people were involved. V. Benda considered it necessary to create a parallel economy, medicine, which would carry out charitable actions, and set up parallel foreign-policy structures. He insisted on the need to create a "parallel policy" - an alternative society in contrast to the state and the authorities that already exist in the country, and thus awaken and unite the civil society that was allegedly in anabiosis under the conditions of the Soviet diktat, antihuman essence of which was not doubted by anyone.

In our opinion, V. Benda's proposals were a reaction to the social isolation of human rights defenders and the general apolitical character of citizens in conditions of ideological pressure of the regime, an attempt to unite the citizens around specific day-to-day affairs under the auspices of human rights protection. Most of the population of the so-called socialist system did not feel the need for such a "parallel society" at the time, except for those who directly suffered from the oppression of the regime. It was impossible to solve the problem of the isolation of the human rights movement in this way, since any obvious manifestations of criticism of the regime and appeals to the observance of the human rights by the authorities immediately caused repression, not only against the immediate protesters, but also with respect to their families, children, and the environment. The social crisis was manifested precisely in the tacit agreement of the majority in exchange for economic stability and relative prosperity, which was offered by the Communist government.

Consequently, in European countries during the second half of the 20th century, there were two trends of scientific thought characterized by peculiar approaches to the definition of social priorities, which were conditioned by political realities and reflected the most important problems of society. Thus, the social component was dominant for western concepts of public administration [11].

From the last third of the 20th century and at the beginning of this century, in democratic countries, the social dominant of the public administration concept ceases to be relevant, whereas the tendency of theorists to determine the structural, functional, and tactical algorithms of the activities of public administration becomes more common. The social component remained important, but as if taken for granted, given the rather high standard of living of the population that has become massively wealthy. Perhaps this is due to the fact that Western countries, where the researchers of this problem mainly come from, have developed and implemented productive social models, offering the population in each

country peculiar but effective approaches to solving the all problem social aspects of life. Most people of the developed countries in Europe were able to satisfy their needs in everyday life and to receive assistance from the state in times of difficulty.

At the same time, philosophers and civil activists from Central and Eastern European countries focused on moral and human rights issues, in particular on the possibilities and techniques of their protection under totalitarian regimes. Their state-building theories were predominantly based on moral argumentation and idealistic concepts that were significantly ahead of time, in particular in defining the role of human rights in modern society.

For Ukraine and other countries of democratic transit, the experience of European administration of the second half of the 20th century offers two main aspects: first, it is necessary to formulate the conceptual foundations of state policy, clearly defining not only the general goal, but also the tools that can ensure its implementation [12]. Government programs must have a scientific basis and developed mechanisms for implementation with clear priorities for society at both the strategic and tactical levels. Secondly, there is a certain algorithm, a certain sequence of government steps that eliminates the chaos of power impulsing. Among any scientifically-based administration concepts, the first ones to be implemented are those that will be aimed at raising the welfare of the population [13].

IV. NEW APPROACHES TO THE INTERACTION OF POWER AND SOCIETY AS A PRIORITIES OF PUBLIC ADMINISTRATION IN THE MODERN PERIOD

New approaches to the interaction of power and society, characteristic of the modern period of development of European countries, deprived of political confrontation after the collapse of the USSR, conditioned the social activity of people to ensure accountability and control of power on the principles of decentralization, deconcentration and professionalism of public administration.

The essence of the new approaches is that civil society is personified by people whose everyday lives enable them to implement moral incentives and practical actions in favor of the society. The authorities do not delegate their functions to the public, but instead engage them in cooperation on the basis of mutual respect and support. A worthwhile tandem of power and civil society is fruitful, due to pragmatic positions, and powerful, given the capacity of both states and communities to act in concert.

In this key, in the early 2000's, the interdisciplinary concept of an effective state became popular, according to which efficiency is understood as the development and support of mechanisms for identifying and consolidating social advantages, focusing on the goals that are shared by society, and the ability to achieve them. Effective government is aware of the limitations of its capabilities and is ready to delegate its powers to agents capable of implementing them with greater efficiency than the center. That is, the state is at the center of economic development, not as a direct source of growth, but

as a partner, catalyst and assistant, shifting the emphasis from the quantitative aspect of economic activity to its qualitative aspect.

The problem of management effectiveness in the concept of organizational development, which, at the turn of the century, raised the questions of structure, corporate culture and organizational activity, was addressed in a peculiar way. The purpose of this concept, which since then has continued to be the subject of discussions, was to increase the efficiency of the functioning of the public administration system, thanks to its adaptability, flexibility and professionalism of civil servants. This concept is particularly relevant for post-socialist countries, whose population still spends a significant part of the time in queues to power cabinets, passes from one official to another, and patiently accepts bureaucratic rudeness, overt disrespect, unprofessionalism, irresponsibility, and at the same time feels absolute powerlessness to change something. A significant part of these and many other shortcomings are inherent in the apparatuses of the "old democracies", the difference is in a scale. British officials also make mistakes. This is in reference to the scope of negative manifestations, their consequences and responsibilities. The high level of organizational culture, appropriate organizational support for administration activities, especially with regard to public services, excludes actions "at his discretion" for the official since the job description provides for any standard turn in the narrow limits of the specialization of the officials' actions. The professionalism of narrowly oriented managers is a positive consequence for both providers and recipients of administrative services, in particular, while introducing opportunities for informational (non-contact) service delivery.

From the end of the 20th century, J. Boston's concept of new public management became popular [14]. It envisages the decentralization of governance through the empowerment and accountability of public administration and local self-government by providing local communities with the opportunity to independently solve their problems and control the quality of services provided by these bodies. This approach correlates with the basic values of local self-government, in particular autonomy (decentralized management), democracy (public participation) and efficiency (proximity of the authorities to the population supporting it). The state delegates the functions of providing public services to non-governmental (commercial, public) organizations, retaining control and development of a common strategy. Such decentralization allows for some flexibility and management efficiency, as well as stimulates competition between service providers and increases civil and social responsibility. At the same time, the emphasis is on the commercialization of the public sector, the increased role of socio-political participation and interaction, did not justify itself in reality.

Particularly relevant in today's context is the concept of the public choice by J. M. Buchanan, which explores the political market along with the economic one, where politicians, voters and government officials interact. The concept of public choice derives from the thesis of the similarity of the logics of political and market behavior, and the motive issue is only

collateral. Representatives of this theory have a negative attitude to state interference in economic life, but argue that the market is not always able to fulfill the role of an effective regulator: "The market "works" badly, but this does not mean that the state "will work "better" [15]. Given that in today's world, the competition of politicians to get the voters support mainly leads to increased state interference in the economy, and through the state programs there is a redistribution of income from the poorest and richest layers of the population in favor of the middle class, smaller, but united political groups can win broader, but unconsolidated, political majority.

His supporters consider it necessary to improve the mechanism of the adoption of political decisions, similar in essence to the choice of decisions on the commodity-money market. By analogy with the traditional market of goods and services, the seller in the political market is a politician, the buyer is a voter, and state bodies are provided with intermediary functions. Politicians offer action program packages, voters vote. There is a peculiar process of buying and selling election programs, which is the essence of modern representative democracy. Awareness of the true essence of pre-election realities makes it possible for citizens to form a peculiar immunity to the manipulation of politicians, analysts, image-makers, and the media, which should contribute to the consolidation of democracy. Researching this issue at the junction of political economy and the theory of public administration, the researchers concluded that in order to adopt social laws, establish taxes, allocate budget funds and make other public decisions in accordance with the needs of society, rather than individuals or business groups, it is necessary to choose not so much a certain policy, such as neo-Keynesian or monetary, etc., but a way of limiting state regulation and control. The concept of public choice is based on the economic approach to the analysis of political processes; that is, it treats political decisions as the choice of alternative ways of exchanging taxes for public goods, although the taxes are paid by some, the benefits go to others. The agreement reached by the participants in the collective choice in politics is similar to the voluntary exchange of individual goods on the market. Public choice theorists propose a new concept of organizing a "political market": reform political procedures and rules so that they contribute to the achievement of universal agreement in society. At the same time, the state does not change or establish rules, but only states the observance or non-compliance with them, and imposes only those sanctions that are foreseen in the constitutional treaty. That is, the state itself does not apply sanctions, but only makes a decision on their implementation [16]. The scale of economic interference of the state, functioning on democratic principles, depends on constitutional restrictions or constitutionally enshrined rules that prohibit the creation of budget deficits or limit their scope. This approach has been adopted by many parliaments of the world. The concept of public choice thus put into question the underlying and influential concepts, in particular the concept of the "welfare economy", "social state" and the concept of "competing groups" as an effective way to make optimal

political decisions [17].

Contemporary trends in the conceptual approaches to public administration in the European Union are determined by a number of universal factors. Among them, in particular: globalization, integration processes in Europe, information revolution, the latest achievements in the field of management and administration technologies. Despite the considerable interest of scientists in the theoretical problems of public administration in different countries of the world, there is still no consensus in the scientific literature on the ability of individual, territorially determined theoretical approaches to ensure the effectiveness of public administration in practice.

Significant regional factors of universalization and convergence of theories of public administration remain the common traditions of European management culture, roughly the same for the most developed European countries socio-economic and political conditions. Specific socio-cultural factors - traditions, customs, psycho-emotional peculiarities of the population, which are individual for each European country - have a significant impact on the situation, while becoming demonstrative under the influence of glocalization and the imperatives of expediency, efficiency and effectiveness of public administration both at the national and at the integration levels.

The main concepts of modern socio-political management, according to J. Kooiman, are "Governing", "Governance" and "Governability", which together form the theory, the essence of which is to permanently reorganize, establish interaction between different participants in state-public relations, establish a balance of social forces and social interests on the basis of mutual trust and understanding [18].

Consequently, the classical approach to public administration, if understood as controlling and guiding actions of governments directed at the formation of a political course in various spheres of society and its implementation through the state apparatus, was enriched with new variants of meaning. In particular, the meaning of the term "government" from "exercising hierarchical control" has expanded to "new governance", which involves non-state structures, creating mixed public-private networks, one way or another involved in managerial processes.

The concept of "Good Governance" is a "framework" model of public administration that was formed in modern Europe. According to the concept of human rights, every person, among other things, has the right to have qualified professional and responsible power. Therefore, the concept of human rights has become a universal basis for modern state governance and the whole complex of processes of functioning of power, the formation and implementation of state policy and state-power relations. The necessity of ensuring human rights determines the processes of making managerial decisions and their implementation at the international (integrational), national, local levels of public administration and self-government and effective interaction between sectors of society.

"Good" or "proper" governance can be consistent with the concept of "effective governance" when it comes to governing

the state, private sector and civil society. At the national level, criteria are set for "good" ("proper", "appropriate") governance, according to the original experience of each country, each nation and their own needs and plans. "Good governance" defines an ideal that is difficult to achieve in its entirety, although this must be sought. Democratization, civil society, decentralization, peaceful conflict resolution and government accountability are characteristics of the concept of good governance that are inherent in effective, democratic public governance. The emphasis on good governance promotes democratic governments in the development of democratic institutions that have endured time trials.

Democratic states of Europe and America have become the most successful ones in the implementation of Good Governance, which is why in these countries state institutions have developed standards of governance that must meet the needs of a modern society and every citizen on the basis of respect for and guarantee of human rights. These standards are characterized by appropriate relations between governments and markets, between governments and citizens, between governments and the private or public sectors, between elected and appointed officials, between local institutions and residents of cities and villages, between the legislative and executive branches of government, and between national states and institutions. These relations are characterized by the expediency of the principles of equilibrium of mutual influences and mutual responsibility.

Mandatory condition for realization of the above-mentioned modern theories of socio-political control is "Governability" as "manageability", "simplicity of management", which correlates with expediency. Governability in the context of public administration means a sufficiently high level of political and institutional stability, decision-making and government efficiency at all levels. This concerns both the continuity of rules and institutions, and the speed of response to the public request, the consistency and effectiveness of management decisions. In practical terms, this is the shortest path between the request from the public and the government's response to this request. In general, it is the potential for further adaptation between the norm and its implementation, between regulation and its results, between supply and demand for politics and administrative services. Governability depends on the quality of management; that is, the level of maturity of the organized society and its ability to rely on the overall responsibility in the implementation of decisions and the art of appropriate management.

Ensuring governability in public administration relies on the strategic core of the government, which should be formed from professional high-level civil servants and at the central level provide services of the highest quality together with the elected politicians in accordance with the adopted state decisions. On the other hand, every government must rely on its own decentralized state infrastructure, each structural element of which, according to J. Kooiman, is responsible for the result, not for the implementation of the procedure, in order to ensure the efficiency of social services at a high scientific level, which is characteristic of modern democracies

[19].

The organic implementation of market management practices and the principles of "good governance" have led to the definition of the main areas of adaptation to the current state of the governing systems of the democratic transition countries. This is in reference to informatization; de-bureaucratization; decentralization; deconcentration; privatization; introduction of economic mechanisms for regulating governing processes; and, introduction of service administration.

The general tool for realization of these directions was the orientation of the activities of state administration bodies at the multidisciplinary concept of governance based on the results. The concept is focused, among other things, on improving the quality of budget services through active cooperation between public authorities and non-profit organizations with the population [20].

In order to realize this concept, in particular in Germany, the desire is to provide high quality public services to the population by creating an effective consumer protection system, introducing special procedures for resolving conflict situations and conducting regular consumer surveys on the quality of services. In the United Kingdom, in this context, the system of "standards for work with citizens" was developed, which includes the definition of performance indicators for civil servants working with the population. The UK State Departments annually develop and report on Best Practices Code indicators on official sites.

Accordingly, in France, each state institution has certain obligations as far as citizens are concerned. In Finland, in order to increase the transparency and efficiency of services provided to the population, they carry out an evaluation of the results of state reform programs based on the analysis of public opinion by the indicators of quality of public services; governability of the public sector; efficiency of public sector activity; motivation of civil servants; qualitative characteristics of the process of implementing administrative reforms; definition of program goals and ways of its realization.

The polemic potential of these approaches is focused, in particular on the concepts of "administrative services", "state services", and "public services", the interpretation of which is rather ambiguous, especially in the context of e-governance.

The introduction of information and technological approaches in communication between citizens and state institutions has led to an increase in the quality of administrative services. New concepts of public administration, focused on high quality of service for the population, take into account the imperatives of the information society. The information paradigm of public administration determines tendencies of treating information as a strategic resource. Proper information provision of management processes is a necessary basis for the adoption of effective managerial decisions.

The main ideas, programs and measures for the application of information and communication technologies in public administration are adopted in EU countries in the form of an e-

government concept, the implementation strategy of which aims to provide the possibility of providing public services mainly through the Internet at all levels of government. The introduction of "E-Government" significantly influenced the theoretical foundations of government, since it brought new concepts, approaches, structural and meaningful innovations and significantly increased the effectiveness of communication of an individual with the state. The issue remains controversial, in particular in the context of observance of human rights in the virtual space.

V. THE DEVELOPMENT OF THE CONCEPTUAL FOUNDATIONS OF THE MODERN MANAGERIAL PROCESS

Integration processes have actualized the problems of multi-level and multi-focal government, which has led to the formation of multidisciplinary concepts devoted to finding the appropriate combination of integrational and national prerogatives of management. At the integration level, an intergovernmental neofunctional approach, in particular, to integration policy, is involved.

An important and effective step in the development of the conceptual foundations of the modern managerial process was the formation of the concept of Political networks and Multi-level governance, which was universalized, in particular, for the European administrative space [21].

The European Union as a political entity is characterized by a multilevel power structure, a significant number of sectors that differ significantly in terms of competences and decision-making methods. This refers to the existence of supranational, national and regional structures that lose the general hierarchy at the integration level and gravitate toward appropriate situational subordination, while at the national, regional and local levels there is a standard scheme of subordination with a tendency to form a new configuration of the national "vertical power structure". The erosion of national peculiarities and the "Europeanization" of state governance processes and structures are ongoing. In this context, the current situation is characterized by a certain crisis of legitimacy regarding the division of competences between supranational and national levels. The formation of new forms of interaction between public authorities of different levels on the EU scale takes place against the background of the fact that the cooperation of supranational and national authorities "erodes" the hierarchical relations of subordination established at national borders, although the legal nature of these processes has not yet been determined definitively or documented [22].

The concept of interactive management defines the multi-key aspects of modern management, in particular, actualizes meta-management as the interaction management and an instrument for realizing meta-management in the conditions of globalization, glocalization and Europeanization of management [23].

Types and methods of social communication that provide modern management interaction with a clearly expressed political aspect, in the theory of state and political analysis of systems, are referred by M. Foucault to competing management models, such as Governmentality, dealing with

the historical and political nature of interaction management. The term "governmentality" is defined as the "art of management" with a clearly expressed qualitative aspect. It is about how the government and the administration conduct management activities; how people (officials) manage or behave themselves, and how these two processes are interconnected. The concept of "governmentality" determines and interconnects the power, market and self-actualization technologies. The latest technologies, for example, revolve around the capabilities of individuals to control and, therefore, manage themselves and the environment on different scales. The guiding force here is not so much the rule of law, but the interest of personal and public benefit and personal responsibility, which is carried out independently of the government on the basis of normalization, which in the simplest sense means life in accordance with established norms and self-esteem, which in its turn means awareness and use of own opportunities on the basis of constant self-esteem, personal discipline and self-improvement. Each technology of the "governmentality" concept can work together with the others or even overlap from time to time, helping to set the boundaries of the role of the government operating in a particular society. Indicative is the emphasis on pluralism, personality and mutual responsibility, which distinguishes the latest approaches to politics and governance.

Such understanding of pluralism is the norm of a the politics designed to respond to a multitude of interests and identities of the present within the limits of social diversity, complexity and dynamics of society as a whole, when politics becomes a medium and an instrument of empowering people and improving the realization of their freedom [24].

The process of forming the concept of multi-level governance illustrates the tendency of the convergence of theory and management practice characteristic of the present, according to which, theoretical generalizations are carried out on the basis of practical steps, and not vice versa. Inclusion of new combinations of social, economic and political interaction that may differ from civil society, the market and the state, causes tension in contemporary society within the framework of interactive management, in particular when based on advisory or discursive policy analysis. By "governmentality", a new communicative policy helps people in society to voice their problems and demand an adequate power response. "Self-organizing network" - "management without government" is typical for users of the Internet, radio and mobile communications.

Within the framework of neo-institutionalism, the network concept analyzes diverse network structures, within which, certain resources are also produced, including information, etc., with personal and informal contacts playing important roles. It is these connections that are treated as a valuable resource in the real world, despite their negative impact on the efficiency of markets and management processes. Government officials are surrounded by concrete people and act under their diverse influences, in particular when making decisions and shaping policies. Granting subsidies, grants, tenders, even the order in the provision of services can be motivated not only by

public interests, but also personal preferences, political positions and friendly relations; in other words, carried out not without a bias. Despite considerable autonomy from the state, networks can be run by officials or political leaders. Networks can be an alternative to a market mechanism and a state hierarchy, such as elites, diasporas, corporate, professional groups, etc.

Consequently, those factors whose general influence on all modern state systems cannot be overestimated and is particularly important for the modern stage of development of the overwhelming majority of the state governance concepts of European countries. In particular:

Integration as a process of convergence of national political structures, aimed at mutual cooperation with the aim of forming a certain integral complex of political systems at the intergovernmental level. One of the characteristic results of integration is the unification of these structures by the mandatory presence of formal as well as informal public institutions for jointly solving common issues. It is believed that the integrated community increases the level of transactions between the participants of integration and possibilities for satisfaction of interests on the basis of common values;

Human rights as the only universally recognized non-confrontational platform for reconciling economic, political and ideological aspirations;

Information and technological changes that offered new, common to all socio-political forces, algorithms of interaction of the individual with the environment, with the authorities and among themselves.

The overwhelming majority of modern public administration concepts are characterized by development of new mechanisms of relations with society, politicians and citizens. The complication of the social structure of society, transformation of civil society into an essential factor in the political life of the society, makes it necessary to seek new mechanisms of relations between public authorities, individuals and organizations that express different interests. Development takes place in two directions: on the one hand, efforts are being made to improve the quality of services provided by the state to the population, in particular in education, health care, social insurance, etc. On the other hand, new mechanisms for involving citizens in the process of adoption and implementation of state decisions are being formed. It promotes efficient use of resources for solving social problems, more accurate identification of the priorities of state policy and satisfying citizens' rights to have a professional, capable and responsible government.

The principles of modern European governance in their applied dimension determine the emphasis on organizational principles that ensure the clarity and effectiveness of administrative procedures based on the competence and responsibility of civil servants. The combination of external influences determines the general tendencies towards universalization and convergence of the conceptual foundations of state systems in the conditions of preservation of traditional national structures, although this thesis is not

devoid of polemical potential.

VI. CONCLUSION

The dynamics of the formation of European governance concepts is characterized by a succession of priorities: from socio-economic and moral-ethical to organizational-procedural and non-hierarchical ones. From the priorities of the "welfare state" to ensure a decent level of material wealth for the people through a "minimum state" with its priorities of human responsibility for their own fate under the conditions of minimal state protection, by emphasizing horizontal ties and redistribution of powers and competences of "effective state" from its developed procedures and limits of responsibility at all levels of government and in close cooperation with civil society - to the priorities of human rights in the concepts of "good governance" and all those which recognize the absolute priority for the governance observance, protection and compliance with human rights.

Scientific thought will continue to offer the society even more advanced concepts, but the fact that at a certain stage of development of public administration, human rights should be its theoretical and methodological basis, and their observance, provision and protection – must be a real indicator of the efficiency of power - is an indisputable fact. To ensure such improvement, the following are needed: the real distribution of powers capable of balancing them; the rule of law, based on the laws that expediently limit individualism to prevent the abuse of rights and freedoms by citizens themselves, as well as unlawful actions of politicians and officials of all branches and at all levels of the government. Mutual responsibility of the state and its citizens on the basis of the appropriate legal relation is capable of defending the rights and freedoms of citizens to ensure the rights and freedoms of the society.

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